

Infrared Spectroscopic Study of Saturation Extracts from Arid-Zone Field Soils Amended with Sewage Sludge[†]

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The surface horizons of two arid-zone field soils that had received amendments of composted, anaerobically-digested sewage sludge for four years were sampled to determine what changes may have occurred in the readily water-soluble fractions of the soils. Infrared spectra of evaporated films prepared from two-hour saturation extracts of the soil samples were interpreted to ascertain these changes. The IR spectra indicated that the majority of the compounds in the saturation extracts were carboxylates, carbonates, and nitrates, regardless of the rate of sludge application or the type of field soil. This result was considered to be an indication of substantial oxidation of the sludge organic compounds in the field soils, in agreement with the finding in a previous laboratory incubation study, that sludge decomposition would be rapid in an alkaline, unsaturated soil.

In a recent study, Schaumberg *et al.*¹ investigated the changes which occurred in the water-soluble fractions of sewage sludge soil mixtures that were incubated in the laboratory for 100 weeks. Infrared spectra of evaporated films prepared from saturation extracts of the sludge-soil mixtures showed that sludge decomposition followed a pattern which involved the disappearance of carbohydrate, protein, sulfonate and sulfate compounds, with the emergence of carboxylates and nitrates. These transformations could be essentially complete in as little as 10 weeks, but were retarded considerably under acidic or water saturated conditions in the incubated soils.

The question remains as to how these conclusions will apply to sludge decomposition under field conditions. In this paper, that question is addressed through an infrared spectroscopic study of the readily water-soluble compounds extracted from the surface horizons of two arid-zone soils that had been used for about four years in field experiments conducted to assess the utility of anaerobically-digested sewage sludge as a soil amendment². The data obtained were expected to give information about the changes in the readily-soluble components of sludge in the soil environment.

Materials and Methods

Soil samples: Surface horizons (0-15 cm) of two soils in randomized experimental plots located at the Moreno Field Station of the University of California, Riverside, were sampled in September 1979. The experimental plots were employed in a long-term field investigation by Chang *et al.*² to ascertain the

utility of anaerobically-digested sewage sludge as a soil amendment. The plots sampled were fallow and had received composted sludge applications at the rate of 0, 10, 20 or 40 ton/acre (0, 22.5, 45.0 or 90.0 mT/ha). The composted sludge was obtained from the Joint Water Pollution Control Plant operated by the Los Angeles County Sanitation Districts.

The composted sludge had been applied twice annually, beginning in the winter of 1975, to plots on Greenfield sandy loam (coarse-loamy, mixed, thermic Typic Haploxeralf) and on Domino loam (fine-loamy, mixed, thermic Xerollic Calciorthud). These plots had received eight sludge applications at the time they were sampled for the present study. During the period of sludge application, all of the field plots were cropped annually with barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and sorghum (*Sorghum vulgare*). Complete details of the field experiments are given by Chang *et al.*².

Some properties of the surface horizons of the two soils investigated are listed in Table 1. Detailed field observations and textural analyses indicated that soil properties were rather uniform across each experimental plot and throughout the upper 15 cm of the soil profile. Chemical analyses showed that almost all (>90%) of the trace metal accumulation from sludge applications on the plots was in the upper 15 cm of the soil profile (Chang *et al.*²). Accordingly, it was expected that studies of the surface soils in the plots would give significant information concerning changes in the applied sludge.

[†] Dedicated to Professor R. C. Mehrotra on the occasion of his sixtieth birthday.

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TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF THE FIELD SOILS (0-15 cm)

Soil Series	Particle size fractions%			CEC meq/100g	Organic C %	CaCO ₃ %	pH (sat paste)
	Sand	Silt	Clay				
Domino	42	35	23	14.0	4.3	1.2	7.8
Greenfield	62	27	11	8.7	0.8	0.0	7.1

Infrared spectral analysis: Saturation extracts of each soil sample were obtained in duplicate as described by Schaumberg *et al.*¹. Aliquots of the extracts were prepared for infrared spectral analysis also as discussed by these authors. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 621 spectrophotometer in the 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ wavenumber range. Interpretation of the spectra was carried out with the assistance of standard references as listed by Schaumberg *et al.*¹. Principal band assignments are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL BAND ASSIGNMENTS IN THE IR SPECTRA OF THE SATURATION EXTRACTS.

Band position cm ⁻¹	Assignment
3400	OH, NH
1650-1550	COO ⁻
1490-1410	CO ₃ ²⁻
1430-1390	NH ₄ ⁺
1400-1310	COO ⁻ , HCO ₃ ⁻
1380-1350	NO ₃ ⁻
1100-900	NH ₄ ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , Ca(NO ₃) ₂ , Si-O
840-815	NO ₃ ⁻ , HCO ₃ ⁻

Results and Discussion

The infrared spectra of the saturation extracts obtained from the field soils are reproduced in Fig. 1 and 2. As in the study by Schaumberg *et al.*¹ the ir spectra represent complex mixtures and are characterized by relatively broad bands. Therefore, specific assignments must be regarded as not completely definitive. However, several general conclusions can be drawn from an examination of the data.

Fig. 1. The ir spectra of saturation extracts taken from the surface horizons of field plots on Domino loam. The sludge application rate is shown with each spectrum.

Fig. 2. The ir spectra of saturation extracts taken from the surface horizons of field plots on Greenfield sandy loam. The sludge application rate is shown with each spectrum.

For the most part, the ir spectra are dominated by bands which can be assigned either to inorganic compounds or to carboxylates. Since sewage sludge is highly organic in nature, this result indicates that there has been a significant transformation of organic material to inorganic compounds (Cf. Fig. 1 of Schaumberg *et al.*¹). All of the ir spectra of the saturation extracts from the treated field plots exhibit bands at about 3400 cm⁻¹, 1610-1635 cm⁻¹, 1415-1430 cm⁻¹, 1340-1360 cm⁻¹, 1040-1065 cm⁻¹ and 815-830 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to OH and NH stretching modes; carboxylate and water; carbonate and ammonium ion; nitrate, bicarbonate, and carboxylate; nitrates and silicates (Si-O stretch); and nitrate and bicarbonate, respectively. The ir spectra of the extracts from the control plots (0 ton acre⁻¹) are quite similar to those of the extracts from the treated plots, with the exception of the lack of a band at approximately 1420 cm⁻¹ in the Greenfield saturation extract. This band, if assigned to carbonate, would be expected to be absent, since the surface horizon of the Greenfield soil does not contain calcium carbonate (Table 1).

A comparison of the ir spectra for the two soils shows that spectra for plots receiving the same application rate of sludge are virtually identical. Thus the spectra for Greenfield composted sludge at 40 ton acre⁻¹ and Domino composted sludge at 40 ton acre⁻¹ are almost superimposable. The obvious conclusion to draw is that the differing characteristics of the soils have not affected dramatically the degradation pattern of the sludge. Since the spectra for the control plots are somewhat different, it is apparent that, in the case of Greenfield soil, the application of the sludge has slightly altered the chemical characteristics of the soil. Since the Greenfield soil is relatively low in organic carbon content (Table 1), and since the sludge is rich in organic material, this finding is not surprising.

The ir spectra also show that, at least up to 40 ton acre⁻¹, the rate of sludge application does not appear to be critical in determining the compounds that appear during decomposition of the sludge. The nature and amount of readily water-soluble compounds in the soils receiving 10 ton acre⁻¹ and those receiving 40 ton acre⁻¹ appear to be similar.

From a qualitative standpoint, the ir spectra obtained in this study are very similar to those obtained for an alkaline, unsaturated soil by Schaumberg *et al*¹ (Fig. 1) at the end of their laboratory incubation study. In both instances it appears as if a significant transformation to highly oxidized organic material or inorganic species has occurred. The ir spectra obtained in the present study indicate that the rate of application of sludge has not altered significantly the composition of the readily water-extractable compounds in the two soils investigated although some changes were noted in the Greenfield soil.

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